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Original Research Article

AN EXCELLENT TANNASE PRODUCTION SOURCE, *ASPERGILLUS ACULEATUS* KUSR2, UNDER SUBMERGED FERMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

A sequential statistical strategy, utilizing Plackett-Burman's factorial design with Design-Expert version 13.0.9, was employed to optimize tannase production from *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 in submerged fermentation. Three variables, incubation period, tannic acid concentration, and concentration of KH₂PO₄ were identified as the most significant parameters. It resulted in an enhanced tannase activity of 50.57(3.73) IU/mL compared to the predicted tannase activity of 49.81 IU/mL. The optimization via response surface methodology resulted in a 2.57-fold increase in tannase production as compared to the amount obtained by the 'one-at-a-time' approach. Results showed that the optimum conditions for tannase production by the mentioned source were 144 h of incubation time, tannic acid 2% (w/v) and KH₂PO₄ 0.3 % (w/v). This optimization, achieved without genetic manipulation, enabled tannase production comparable to the best among published results to provide an excellent source of Tannase with commercial implications.

Keywords: Tannin acyl hydrolase, Response surface, Optimization, *Aspergillus*, Submerged fermentation

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1. Introduction

Tannase also called tannin acyl hydrolase, is an inducible enzyme that catalyzes the hydrolysis of depside and ester bonds in various substrates such as gallo tannins, gallic acid esters, epicatechin gallate, and epigallocatechin-3-gallate, releasing glucose and gallic acid. Tannase is found to have industrial applications in the food, beverage, brewing, cosmetic, pharmaceuticals, and wastewater treatment and chemical industries [1]. Tannase facilitates the transformation of tea catechins, increasing antioxidant activity and improving overall sensory acceptance of tea products [2]. Tannase is used to improve the quality of beverages such as fruit juices, beer, and wine through the removal of tannins, which can contribute to astringency and bitterness [3, 4]. Moreover, tannase has pharmaceutical applications, as it can be used for the production of gallic acid, a compound with antioxidant [5], antibacterial, anti-biofilm activities and anti-inflammatory properties [6], and application in dye removal from wastewater [7]. In addition, Gallic acid and its related compounds have been shown to exhibit numerous health enhancing properties, eliciting powerful antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, gastro-protective, anticancer, cardio-protective, and neuroprotective effects. In the food industry, gallic acid and some of its derivatives (such as lauryl gallate, propyl gallate, octyl gallate, tetradecyl gallate, and hexadecyl gallate) are utilized as antioxidants and preservatives because of their effective ability to scavenge free radicals and their strong antioxidant properties [8]. Fungal tannase, has garnered significant attention due to its potential applications and industrial production. Fungal tannase producers have been extensively studied, and various fungal strains have been identified that can produce this enzyme. The fungal genera known to produce tannase include *Aspergillus* [9, 10, 11], *Penicillium* [12, 13], *Rhizopus* [14], *Paecilomyces variotii* [15] and yeast [16, 17]. The microorganisms commonly used for tannase production are filamentous fungi of the genus *Aspergillus* [18, 19] and *Penicillium* [20, 21]. These fungi have been the subject of extensive research to understand their tannase production pathways, optimize culture conditions, and develop efficient fermentation processes for large-scale production.

Submerged fermentation is an effective method for optimizing tannase production, offering precise control over culture conditions, higher yields, scalability, and improved cost-effectiveness, making it an advantageous choice for industrial tannase production [22, 23]. The statistical optimization of the various parameters through experimental design methodologies such as Plackett–Burman’s factorial design and Response Surface Methodology enables the identification of optimal conditions for maximal tannase production. By statistically optimizing tannase production, researchers and industrial practitioners can ensure higher yields of this valuable enzyme, leading to cost-effectiveness and improved efficiency in its industrial applications. Moreover, the systematic approach offered by statistical optimization contributes to the reproducibility and scalability of tannase production processes, making it an essential aspect of industrial enzyme production [28, 29]. As there are no reports on the *Aspergillus aculeatus* as a source for tannase enzyme production, it would be important to conduct further research to investigate the potential of *Aspergillus aculeatus* as a source for tannase enzyme production. In this study Plackett–Burman and central composite design of response surface methodology were used to investigate the influence of medium constituents and cultivation parameters to improve the yield of tannase from *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2.

2. Materials and Methods

All the chemicals and media ingredients were of analytical grade and purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Sigma Chemical, and Sisco Research Laboratory, Mumbai, India.

2.1 Microorganism

The tannase producing fungal culture, *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 (GenBank Accession no.MN416237.1) was isolated from Western Ghats forest soil sample from Kerala (11.827167N, 75.702154E, 114° SE, Altitude

73m), India and identified as *Aspergillus aculeatus*, based on 5.8S rRNA ITS gene sequencing and used for tannase production.

2.2 Production media

The basal media components include (g/L) tannic acid: 10, NaNO₃: 3, KCl: 0.52, MgSO₄ .7H₂O: 0.52, KH₂PO₄: 1.52 [24]. Tannic acid solution was prepared separately, with 0.1 M NaOH, pH: 4.5 ± 0.2, sterilized by filtering through a sterile membrane filter (pore size 0.2 µm) and added to the medium to have a final tannic acid concentration of 1%. A unit approximately 2 x 10⁷ spores/mL was added to the 100 mL of pre sterilized medium for the production of tannase enzyme and incubated for 7 days in an orbital shaker incubator (Labline) at 30 °C at 100 rpm. The culture was centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 15 min to obtain the extra cellular enzyme.

2.3 Tannase assay

Tannase activity was estimated using the method of Sharma et al. 2000 [25]. The method is based on the formation of chromogen between gallic acid (released by the action of tannase on methyl gallate) and rhodanine (2-thio-4-ketothiazolidine). Tannase assay procedure includes the addition of 0.2 mL of crude enzyme to 0.55 mL of citrate buffer (0.05 M, pH 5). This was followed by the addition of 0.25 mL methyl gallate (0.01 M), 0.3 mL methanolic rhodanine (0.067% w/v), and 0.2 mL of potassium hydroxide (0.5 M) solution with incubation at 30 °C for 5 min after each addition. Diluted the reaction mixture with 4 mL of distilled water and again incubated at 30 °C for 10 min. The pink color developed was read at 520 nm using Spectrophotometer (VARIOSKAN LUX, Thermo Fisher). A set of blanks and controls was used simultaneously. One unit of tannase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to liberate 1 µM of gallic acid/min under defined reaction conditions. Enzyme activity was expressed as IU/mL.

2.4 Preliminary optimization using one factor at a time method (OFAT)

Initial parameter optimization was carried out using traditional one factor at a time (OFAT) method. Various parameters such as incubation time, concentration of tannic acid, incubation temperature, initial pH of the media, agitation, carbon and nitrogen sources, and various salts and minerals were used. Each parameter was assessed for its influence on the tannase production.

2.5 Optimization of tannase production through statistical methods.

Optimization procedure and experimental designs were performed by Plackett-Burman's factorial design and Response Surface Analysis using Central Composite Design.

2.6 Plackett–Burman's (PB) factorial design

Plackett–Burman's factorial design is an efficient technique for medium component selection [30]. It was used to determine the factors that significantly influence the tannase production. From the results obtained on OFAT method, nine independent variables, including incubation period (96 -144 h), tannic acid concentration (2 - 3% w/v), rate of agitation (125 - 200 rpm), pH (6 - 7), temperature (30 - 40 °C), concentration of sucrose (2 - 4% w/v), KCl (0.05 - 0.15% w/v), MgSO₄.7H₂O (0.1 - 0.2% w/v) and, KH₂PO₄ (0.1 - 0.3% w/v), were analysed in 12 experimental runs (Table 1). All the experiments were carried out in triplicate. The responses of these factors for the production of tannase were analysed at the low level (-1) and high level (+1). The statistical software package 'Design Expert (ver. 13.0.9, State-Ease Design, USA)' was used for analysing the experimental data. Plackett–Burman's design is based on the first- order polynomial model:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i$$

Where Y is the response (tannase activity in IU/mL), β_0 is the model intercept and β_i is the linear coefficient for independent variable X_i . Though P-B design analyses the major factors influencing tannase activity, it doesn't study the interaction among the factors. Regression analysis was performed. The **Model F-value** of 80.94 implies the model is significant. There is only a 1.23% chance that an F- value of this magnitude could occur as noise. The results of the Analysis of variance showed a p value less than 0.05, which indicated that the model is significant. The factors with positive linear coefficient value and p value less than 0.05, were selected for the next level of optimization. Those factors with negative linear coefficient values and positive linear coefficient values, but p value greater than 0.05 were considered insignificant and were kept at mid-level in the next level of optimization.

Table 1. PB design with coded level

Variables	Units	Coded levels	
		Low	High
Time period	h	96	144
Tannic acid	% (w/v)	2	3
Agitation	rpm	125	200
Temperature	°C	30	40
Sucrose	% (w/v)	2	4
KCl	% (w/v)	0.05	0.15
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	% (w/v)	0.1	0.2
KH ₂ PO ₄	% (w/v)	0.1	0.3
pH		6	7

2.7 Response surface analysis using Central Composite Design (CCD)

The variables with significant effects on tannase production, were further evaluated using a central composite design (CCD). The CCD model helps to study the interactions between the variables, and RSM helps to explore the interactions between the selected variables. Out of the nine factors selected for the P-B, three factors (incubation time, concentration of tannic acid and KH₂PO₄) were selected for CCD and were studied at five levels. The response measured was the yield value of the tannase enzyme. The coded values for independent variable were $-\alpha$ (lowest level), $+\alpha$ (highest level), 0 (mid-level), +1 and -1 represents the intermediate values between lowest, middle and highest values (Table 2). Twenty experimental runs were carried out, and all the experiments were performed in triplicate, and the values reported are the mean of three independent experiments. CCD follows second order polynomial equation represented as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_{ij}$$

Where Y is the response; β_0 is the coefficient of fitted response at the center point of the design; and β_i -coefficients of linear terms, β_{ii} -coefficients of square terms, and β_{ij} - coefficients of interactive terms, respectively. X_i 's were A, B, and C; X_i^2 were A², B² and C²; and X_{ij} 's were AB, AC, and BC (A- incubation time, B- tannic acid, C- KH₂PO₄).

Table 2. Coded variables for CCD

Coded variables	Levels				
	- α	+1	0	-1	+ α
Incubation time (h)	79.63	96	120	144	160.36
Tannic acid (%)	1.65	2	2.5	3	3.34
KH ₂ PO ₄ (%)	0.03	0.1	0.2	0.3	1.306

2.8 Validation of the experimental model

To validate the model equation, experiments were conducted in triplicate for tannase enzyme production under optimum conditions and the results obtained empirically were compared to the response (enzyme produced) predicted by the model.

3 Results and Discussion

Present study deals with the one variable at a time optimization of tannase production from *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2. The method involves the optimization of various parameters by keeping previously optimized parameters constant. (Table 3). The optimum incubation period for tannase production was found to be 120 h, during which the enzyme reached a concentration of 6.47 ± 0.45 IU/mL, showing maximum activity at this point. Addition of tannic acid also increases the production significantly, up to 11.01 ± 0.62 at a concentration of 2.5% w/v, showing a significant improvement in yield and demonstrating its effectiveness as an additive. The agitation rate of the production media showed an increase in the production to 11.50 ± 0.64 IU/mL, demonstrating improved productivity. The optimum temperature for the enzyme activity was found to be 35 °C, with an enzyme activity of 13.53 ± 0.73 IU/mL. Among the carbon sources that were optimized, sucrose at 3% showed maximum activity of 15.96 ± 0.66 IU/mL. Various nitrogen sources were optimized, and it was found that urea gave the maximum enzyme production with a yield of 16.87 ± 0.93 IU/mL. Potassium chloride, magnesium sulfate, and potassium dihydrogen phosphate concentration are critical factors affecting enzyme activity. The specific concentrations that have been found to be effective for promoting enzyme activity are 0.1% w/v potassium chloride (17.15 ± 0.55 IU/mL), 0.15% w/v magnesium sulfate (17.17 ± 0.12 IU/mL), and 0.2% w/v potassium dihydrogen phosphate (19.64 ± 0.49 IU/mL) (**Fig.a-l**).

Table 3. Maximum tannase activity obtained in OFAT

Parameters	Tannase activity IU/mL (SD)
Incubation period (120 h)	6.4 (0.45)
pH (6.5)	9.57 (0.72)
Tannic acid (2.5% w/v)	11.01 (0.62)
Agitation (125 rpm)	11.50 (0.64)
Temperature (35 °C)	13.53 (0.73)
Sucrose (3% w/v)	15.96 (0.66)
Urea (1% w/v)	16.87 (0.93)
Potassium chloride (0.1% w/v)	17.15 (0.55)
Magnesium sulphate (0.15% w/v)	17.17 (0.12)
Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (0.2% w/v)	19.64 (0.49)

Figure a

Figure b

Figure c

Figure d

Figure e

Figure f

Figure g

Figure h

Figure i

Figure j

Figure k

Figure l

Fig a-l: Tannase production during OFAT

3.1 Optimization of *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 tannase using statistical optimization.

Plackett-Burman's design

The design matrix for the screening of significant variables for enzyme production and the mean value of the corresponding responses are shown in Table 4.

As results observed in Table 4, a wide range of production ranging from 2.86 ± 0.13 IU/mL to 42.18 ± 1.85 IU/mL was observed during the trials. Trial 10 produced the maximum activity 42.18 ± 1.85 IU/mL. After performing the analysis, the results were evaluated.

Table 4. Plackett–Burman experimental design matrix for screening of important variables for tannase production using *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2

Run	Incubation period (h)	Tannic acid (% w/v)	Agitation (rpm)	Temperature °C	Sucrose % w/v	KCl (% w/v)	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (% w/v)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (w/v)	pH	Tannase activity IU/mL (SD)
1	96	3	125	40	4	0.05	0.2	0.3	7	15.56 (1.42)
2	96	2	200	30	4	0.15	0.1	0.3	7	16.42 (0.83)
3	144	3	125	40	4	0.15	0.1	0.1	6	32.89 (1.63)
4	96	2	125	40	2	0.15	0.2	0.1	7	07.49 (0.31)
5	96	2	125	30	2	0.05	0.1	0.1	6	14.64 (0.96)
6	96	3	200	30	4	0.15	0.2	0.1	6	02.86 (0.13)
7	96	3	200	40	2	0.05	0.1	0.3	6	24.26 (1.84)
8	144	3	200	30	2	0.05	0.2	0.1	7	08.98 (0.24)
9	144	2	200	40	4	0.05	0.1	0.1	7	17.15 (0.73)
10	144	3	125	30	2	0.15	0.1	0.3	7	42.18 (1.85)
11	144	2	200	40	2	0.15	0.2	0.3	6	12.52 (0.86)
12	144	2	125	30	4	0.05	0.2	0.3	6	08.18 (0.16)

The first order linear model obtained for the production of tannase enzyme can be written as:

$$\text{Response (Y)} = 16.93 + 3.39 \text{ incubation period} + 4.19 \text{ Tannic acid} - 3.23 \text{ Agitation} + 1.38 \text{ Temperature} - 1.42 \text{ Sucrose} + 2.13 \text{ KCl} - 7.66 \text{ MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O} + 2.93 \text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4 + 1.04 \text{ pH}.$$

The R² value obtained was found to be 0.9973 and adjusted R² to be 0.9849. Among the nine variables, period, concentration of tannic acid and KH₂PO₄ were having positive linear co-efficient and p value < 0.05, and thus considered significant and were selected for next level of optimization, whereas, agitation and concentration of MgSO₄·7H₂O were having p value < 0.05, but have negative linear coefficient values and temperature, concentration of sucrose and pH have p value > 0.05, and thus they were considered insignificant and excluded from the next level of optimization (Table 5, Table 6).

Table 5. ANOVA for PB design

Factor	Coefficient Estimate	F- value	P- value
Model		80.94	0.0123 Significant
Time period	3.39	71.93	0.0136
Tannic acid	4.19	110.16	0.0090
Agitation	-3.23	65.30	0.0150
Temperature	1.38	12.00	0.0742
Sucrose	-1.42	12.58	0.0711
KCl	2.13	28.48	0.0334
MgSO47H2O	-7.66	367.69	0.0027
KH2PO4	2.93	53.61	0.0181
pH	1.04	6.72	0.1221

Table 6. Fit Statistics of PB Design

Model terms	Values
Std.Dev	1.38
Mean	16.93
C.V. %	8.18
R ²	0.9973
Adjusted R ²	0.9849
Predicted R ²	0.9014
Adeq Precision	31.1162

3.3 Central Composite Design

One of the key hurdles for biochemical engineers is finding a reliable method to produce high-quality enzymes at a low cost. Fermentation optimization plays a crucial role in industrial enzymatic processes by using statistical methods to identify the most important factors and their interactions. RSM was done by using CCD design which showed the interactive effects of three independent variables (incubation period, tannic acid concentration, KH₂PO₄ concentration). The 20-run experiment was performed using the statistical software package 'Design Expert (ver. 13.0.9, State-Ease Design, USA)' for analysing the experimental data. The CCD experimental design with its enzyme production as response has been shown in Table 7. The analysis of variance (ANOVA), and the quadratic regression equation was applied for prediction of tannase enzyme production (Table 8). A range of enzyme production from 24.37 ± 0.75 IU/mL to 49.80 ± 0.63 IU/mL was obtained. The tannase production reaches maximum of 49.80± 3.65 IU/mL when time period increases to 144 h, average concentration of tannic acid (2% w/v) and high concentration (0.3% w/v) of KH₂PO₄ (run no.16, Table 7).

The ANOVA for the CCD design was performed. The **Model F-value** of 9.42 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.08% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. (Table 8 and 9). The variables, C, AB, AC, A² and C² have p value less than 0.05, and thus, considered significant. The model fitness could be expressed by the coefficient of determination R² value. R² value was found to be 0.8945 and which shows a reasonable agreement with that of Adjusted and Predicted R² values the 0.7995 and 0.7243 respectively, which indicates that the model could explain 10.55% of the variability. However, **Adequate**

Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable, in the present model design ratio of 12.7173 indicates an adequate signal and further, this can be applied to navigate design space.

The Lack of Fit F-value of 0.23 implies the Lack of Fit is not significant relative to the pure error. The lack of fit value was found to be insignificant relative to the pure error (p value = 0.9337), which indicated the accuracy of the model. (Table 8)

The quadratic second order polynomial model can be expressed as:

Response (Y) = 32.01 - 1.39A - 0.7767B + 2.34C - 3.31AB + 6.02AC - 2.26BC - 2.45A² + 1.51B² + 2.63C²
 Where, A is incubation period, B is concentration of Tannic acid and C is the concentration of KH₂PO₄.

Table 7. CCD Experimental design and corresponding responses of CCD, represented as mean value with Standard deviation

RUN	FACTORS			ACTUAL ACTIVITY (SD)	PREDICTED ACTIVITY
	Incubation period (h)	Tannic acid (% w/v)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (% w/v)		
1	120	2.5	0.03	37.24 (1.35)	35.52
2	96	3	0.1	39.46 (3.16)	40.80
3	120	3.34	0.2	35.02 (2.98)	34.97
4	160.3	2.5	0.2	27.72 (2.15)	27.43
5	120	1.65	0.2	39.43 (1.33)	37.58
6	144	2	0.1	27.02 (1.70)	28.56
7	120	2.5	0.2	35.87 (2.48)	32.01
8	96	3	0.3	29.09 (0.80)	28.90
9	96	2	0.1	26.99 (2.42)	31.20
10	120	2.5	0.2	27.72 (1.25)	32.01
11	79.63	2.5	0.2	24.37 (0.75)	22.76
12	96	2	0.3	26.90 (1.46)	28.35
13	120	2.5	0.2	30.15 (2.70)	32.01
14	144	3	0.3	36.96 (1.16)	37.10
15	120	2.5	0.2	32.62 (1.56)	32.01
16	144	2	0.3	49.80 (3.63)	49.81
17	120	2.5	0.2	28.47 (1.38)	32.01
18	120	2.5	0.2	36.90 (1.98)	32.01
19	120	2.5	1.30	43.56 (2.60)	43.38
20	144	3	0.1	25.01 (1.88)	24.91

Table 8. ANOVA for response surface quadratic model for the production of tannase

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F -value	p-value
Model	767.17	9	85.24	9.42	0.0008 Significant
A-Time period	26.39	1	26.39	2.92	0.1185
B-Tannic acid	8.24	1	8.24	0.9104	0.3625
C-KH ₂ PO ₄	74.51	1	74.51	8.23	0.0167
AB	87.85	1	87.85	9.71	0.0110
AC	290.28	1	290.28	32.08	0.0002
BC	41.00	1	41.00	4.53	0.0592
A ²	86.17	1	86.17	9.52	0.0115
B ²	32.75	1	32.75	3.62	0.0863
C ²	99.68	1	99.68	11.02	0.0078
Residual	90.49	10	9.05		0.9337
Lack of fit	16.92	5	3.38	0.2301	not significant
Pure Error	73.56	5	14.71		
Cor Total	857.65	19			

Table 9. Coefficients in terms of coded factors

Factor	Coefficient Estimate	Df	Standard Error	95% CI Low	95% CI High	VIF
Intercept	32.01	1	1.23	29.28	34.74	
A-Time period	1.39	1	0.8140	-0.4236	3.20	1.0000
B- Tannic acid	-0.7767	1	0.8140	-2.59	1.04	1.0000
C-KH ₂ PO ₄	2.34	1	0.8140	0.5221	4.15	1.0000
AB	-3.31	1	1.06	-5.68	-0.9441	1.0000
AC	6.02	1	1.06	3.65	8.39	1.0000
BC	-2.26	1	1.06	-4.63	0.1059	1.0000
A ²	-2.45	1	0.7924	-4.21	-0.6797	1.02
B ²	1.51	1	0.7924	-0.2581	3.27	1.02
C ²	2.63	1	0.7924	0.8645	4.40	1.02

To investigate the interaction and visualize the effects of the two factors on tannase activity in a better manner, a graphical representation of RSM (a) and contour plots (b) are presented. On the basis of the result obtained on CCD experiments, the interactions among the variables were pictured as response surface plots (Fig.1a-c) and contour plots (Fig. 2a-c). The effect of two independent variables for tannase enzyme production was displayed, while the third variable was kept at zero-coded level. The observation showed that among the various tested medium components, the cumulative effect of incubation period and KH₂PO₄ concentration is highly significant with 'p' value 0.0002 and with higher 'f' value 32.08 as well as the linear effect of KH₂PO₄ is significant with 'p' value 0.0167 and 'f' value 8.23. This shows as we increase the incubation period and KH₂PO₄ concentration tannase production would increase as cumulative effect of components, as in the case of linear effect of KH₂PO₄ concentration increase the production level of tannase. The relationship between the experimental and predicted values for observed and predicted tannase activity was displayed in Fig. 3, and the data points located close to the diagonal line suggesting a satisfactory

correlation. The Response surface plots and 2D contour plots were generated, which showed the individual and cumulative effect of independent variables as well as probable correlations occurring between incubation period, tannic acid concentration, and KH_2PO_4 concentration on tannase production, by keeping other at its central point. If there is a significant interaction, the contour lines will not be circular; they may be elongated or form ellipses. Contour lines connect points with the same response value and tightly packed lines indicate a steep change, while widely spaced lines indicate a gradual change. At the lower level of incubation period and tannic acid, only 26.99 ± 2.42 IU/mL was obtained, whereas 49.80 ± 3.63 of tannase production was found with higher concentration of above variables. The significant interactive effect of two independent variables time period, and tannic acid, (Fig. 2a and Fig.3a) indicates that by increasing incubation period and tannic acid concentration have a favourable impact on tannase production, it gradually increased with time period. The significant interactive effect of incubation period and KH_2PO_4 concentration on tannase production was found as its concentration increases. (Fig.1b and Fig.2b). No significant interaction was found in the ANOVA by tannic acid concentration and KH_2PO_4 concentration (Fig.1c and Fig.2c). From the curves, it is clearly indicated that the mutual interaction was prominent among factors. The predicted results from the point prediction method showed that maximum tannase production 39.24 was obtained when fermentation was carried out with 120 h of incubation, 2.5% w/v tannic acid and 0.2% w/v KH_2PO_4 .

Fig.1a

Fig.1b

Fig.1c

Fig.1a-c Response surface plots for production of tannase. Interaction between the variables, incubation period vs concentration of tannic acid (a), concentration of tannic acid vs concentration of KH_2PO_4 (b) and time period vs concentration of KH_2PO_4 (c).

Fig.2a

Fig.2b

Fig.2c

Fig.2a-c Contour plots for the production of tannase. Interaction between the variables, time period vs concentration of tannic acid (a), concentration of tannic acid vs concentration of KH_2PO_4 (b) and time period vs concentration of KH_2PO_4 (c).

Fig.3

The maximum tannase activity was observed at a temperature of 35 °C and tannase activity was maximum in the acidic pH range [26]. These results are well supported by earlier findings [27]. Optimum Tannic acid concentration and temperature are also in line with earlier reports [28, 29]. Optimum time period of tannase production (144 h) also agreed with similar findings [30]. These findings make our study more reliable and suitable for low cost production of tannase in submerged fermentation.

3.4 Validation of the model

After CCD analysis, we kept an experiment run of no.16 (Table 7) with; 144 h of incubation, 2.0% w/v tannic acid, and 0.3% w/v KH_2PO_4 for tannase production by *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2, with predicted tannase activity of 49.81 IU/mL. The mean activity obtained from the optimized production medium was 50.57 ± 3.73

(Table.10), which is almost near to the predicted activity. Which can be achieved by optimal values of media components. Upon validation, *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 produces 50.57 ± 3.73 IU/mL tannase activity, which is 2.57 times of the optimized media by the one variable at a time method. Therefore, the CCD design is successfully used for screening various medium components that enhance the tannase yield >2 times. Consequently, the proposed model was thoroughly evaluated and deemed to be highly accurate and reliable for predicting the production of tannase by *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 in various conditions.

Table 10. Enzyme production under optimum condition (SD=Standard deviation)

Trial	Activity (IU/mL)	Mean Activity (IU/mL) \pm SD
1	54.45	50.57 \pm 3.73 IU/mL
2	46.99	
3	50.26	

Great variations in tannase yields can be found with many of its optimized production protocols. It could be attributed to factors such as the choice of microbial strain, fermentation conditions, substrate used, and the presence of mutagenesis or genetic modifications. Hence, the significance of a tannase production system may be valued considering the factors mentioned above. The present study may be compared with the report of Purohit et al. [48] who investigated strain improvement for tannase production using a co-culture of *Aspergillus foetidus* and *Rhizopus oryzae*. They achieved the highest tannase activity of 53.6 IU/mL after 30 hours of incubation with the mutant strain SCPR 337. The achievement of Purohit et al. with strain improvement and other manipulations is only coming to the level of the present achievement of *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 giving tannase production of 50.57(3.73) IU/mL. The present achievement is without any manipulation and only by optimization of conditions. Hence, *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2, the source of tannase in the present optimized system, without any specific manipulation may be considered as an excellent source of tannase, since it produces the enzyme at 50.57(3.73) IU/mL, equal to the achievement of Purohit et al. It may give great dividends in tannase production by introducing various manipulations.

4. Conclusion

Tannase production from *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2 in submerged fermentation was optimized through one variable at a time and a series of statistical methodologies. The results of the study showed that the optimum conditions for tannase production were as follows: 144 h of incubation time, tannic acid at a concentration of 2% (w/v), urea at a concentration of 1% (w/v), KH_2PO_4 at 0.3% (w/v), $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 0.15% (w/v), KCl at 0.1% (w/v), sucrose at a concentration of 3% (w/v), pH maintained at 6.5, inoculum density set to be 2×10^7 spores/mL, agitation rate kept constant at 150 rpm and temperature maintained at 35°C. Under these optimized conditions, satisfactory maximum activity was observed reaching up to 50.57 ± 3.73 IU/mL. In the pre-optimized condition, the enzyme production was found to be 5.38 ± 0.12 IU/mL, which increases approximately by 10 times due to the implementation of statistical optimization methods. The tannase activity was found to be 2.57 times higher compared to the amount obtained by the 'one-at-a-time' approach, (19.64 ± 0.49 IU/mL) by *Aspergillus aculeatus* KUSR2, which is considerably better than the previously reported. The optimized conditions resulted in a significant increase in tannase production, demonstrating the effectiveness of response surface methodology in enhancing enzyme yield. The present endeavour brings up an excellent source of Tannase with commercial implication.

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